

Species 1: *H. erato*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.88; high PNT

NOT test

PC1, PNT.index: 0.32; high PNT

Species 2: *H. chesteronii*

Environmental overlap

PC1
Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.45

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.040

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

Species 1: *H. erato*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.86; high PNT

NDT test

Species 2: *H. chesteronii*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.2; moderate PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1
Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.371

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.057

Background 2->1

D
p.value = 0.60878

Background 1->2

D
p.value = 0.69261